

IMPACT OF ONLINE EDUCATION AMONG THE MBA STUDENTS DURING COVID-19 – A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic necessitated the rapid transition to online teaching, significantly impacting MBA students' educational experiences. This abstract provides a comprehensive overview of the impact of online teaching on MBA students during the pandemic. The study examines both the advantages and challenges faced by students in this new learning environment, shedding light on their academic performance, engagement, and overall satisfaction. Online teaching has offered MBA students newfound flexibility, allowing them to manage their time effectively and access course materials conveniently. Additionally, virtual platforms have facilitated collaboration and networking opportunities, expanding students' professional networks. However, challenges have emerged, including decreased social interaction, feelings of isolation, reduced motivation, and technical difficulties. The study highlights the importance of innovative instructional strategies, faculty training, and reliable technical infrastructure for successful implementation. Understanding the impact of online teaching is crucial for educational institutions to enhance the quality of remote learning and establish resilient educational models for future disruptions. By addressing the identified challenges and capitalizing on the benefits, institutions can improve online teaching methodologies and promote effective online education for MBA students.

Keywords: Online teaching, COVID-19, virtual collaboration, networking, social interaction

INTRODUCTION:

The COVID-19 pandemic emerged at the beginning of 2020, causing a severe global health crisis that had a substantial impact on practically all elements of civilization. One of the sectors most seriously damaged by the earthquake was the education sector. As nations tried to control the epidemic, educational institutions faced a hitherto unheard-of challenge: how to preserve learning while ensuring the health and safety of students and staff. In response, educational institutions swiftly changed their emphasis to online education, ushering in a new

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era in the dissemination and acquisition of knowledge. Since this transition to virtual learning upended traditional classroom-based education and necessitated a paradigm shift in pedagogy and student learning, it was particularly revolutionary for MBA students enrolled in prestigious business administration schools. This introduction investigates the enormous influence of online education on MBA students during the COVID-19 epidemic, delving into the numerous ramifications that developed during this exceptional moment. The abrupt shift to virtual learning brought both obstacles and possibilities for MBA students, who found themselves traversing unfamiliar ground as they transitioned to the digital arena. Using cutting-edge technology, MBA students accessed online lectures, interactive discussions, and course materials from the comfort of their homes, breaking the conventional boundaries of geographical limitations and opening up new avenues of flexibility in learning.

The pandemic-induced change in education promoted a global perspective that expanded their learning experiences as MBA students from many cultural backgrounds and geographies convened in virtual classes. Global connectivity enabled students to engage in cross-cultural dialogue and engagement, allowing them to develop a more thorough grasp of worldwide business methods and difficulties. However, the lack of face-to-face contacts and physical presence presented a distinct set of obstacles for MBA students as they struggled to establish personal connections with classmates and professors via creative digital methods. In this digital context, maintaining student engagement and promoting collaborative learning experiences have become critical goals for educational institutions. MBA students showed resiliency, flexibility, and tenacity in facing the pandemic's risks throughout this transformative journey. They successfully juggled their personal and professional obligations, embraced digital learning tools, mastered virtual teamwork, and quickly adjusted to the ever-changing corporate world dynamics. With their newly acquired knowledge and experiences, MBA students are now prepared to succeed in a workplace that prioritizes technology.

The effects of online education on MBA students provide important insights for the future of higher education as the globe progressively emerges from the grip of the epidemic. Blended learning models, which combine the advantages of online learning with the special advantages of in-person interactions, have been made possible by the increasing use of technology in education. Furthermore, the lessons discovered during this transformational time will surely alter the course of education, redefining the function of technology in creating tomorrow's

business leaders. As a result of online learning, MBA students have seen nothing short of a revolution during the COVID-19 epidemic. This journey has been filled with obstacles, learning opportunities, and an unrelenting dedication to study against the odds.

OVERVIEW OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND ITS DISRUPTION TO EDUCATION:

Beginning in early 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic, which was brought on by the brand-new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, quickly swept across continents and claimed millions of lives. Governments enacted stringent measures to stop the virus's spread as countries battled to manage it, such as statewide lockdowns and social segregation rules. The pandemic had a significant negative influence on a number of societal facets, including education, in addition to the healthcare industry. In order to maintain learning while protecting the health and safety of teachers and students, educational institutions throughout the world confronted an unprecedented challenge. As the epidemic worsened, traditional classroom-based education was rendered impractical, leading colleges and institutions to quickly switch to online education as a substitute form of instruction. This change presented particular difficulties for MBA students who were pursuing postgraduate degrees in business administration and mainly relied on in-person contacts, group projects, and networking opportunities.

Due to the disruption caused by the epidemic, learning took place mostly online as MBA students quickly became used to digital platforms, video conferencing, and asynchronous learning. There were difficulties, including changes in technology, a lack of resources, and possible problems with student connection and participation in virtual environments. However, the change also brought with it opportunities and innovations, enabling MBA students to access course materials remotely, encouraging flexibility in balancing their studies with personal and professional obligations, and bridging geographical boundaries for a global exchange of perspectives. Throughout this transformational time, educational institutions and MBA students showed flexibility and resiliency.

While students demonstrated their resolve to succeed in a learning environment that is continually changing, faculty members embraced pedagogical advances to give excellent virtual training. The experiences and knowledge gained during this time have laid the road for education's future, with blended learning models and reinvented methods of MBA education potentially influencing the next generation of business leaders. In this conference paper, we

examine the problems, possibilities, and consequences that occurred as a result of online education's diverse effects on MBA students during the COVID-19 epidemic. Through this investigation, we hope to learn more about MBA students' resilience and flexibility as well as the creative steps taken by educational institutions to provide a successful learning environment during trying circumstances. Furthermore, we consider how the knowledge gained from this pivotal time might shape MBA education going forward and the larger picture of higher education in the post-pandemic era.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDYING THE IMPACT OF ONLINE EDUCATION ON MBA STUDENTS:

- 1. Unprecedented Educational Shift:** The COVID-19 pandemic led to an unprecedented and rapid transition from traditional classroom-based learning to online education. Understanding the impact of this sudden shift on MBA students provides insights into the challenges and opportunities of virtual education in times of crisis.
- 2. Future of Education:** The pandemic forced educational institutions to adapt swiftly to online learning. Examining the experiences of MBA students during this period can inform the future of education, particularly in terms of incorporating technology and blended learning models into higher education.
- 3. Resilience and Adaptability:** MBA students demonstrated remarkable resilience and adaptability during the pandemic, navigating the uncertainties and complexities of virtual learning. Studying their responses can shed light on effective coping strategies and preparedness for future disruptions.
- 4. Student Engagement and Interaction:** Traditional MBA programs have emphasized networking and face-to-face interactions. Analyzing the impact of virtual classrooms on student engagement and interaction provides valuable insights into fostering collaborative learning experiences in online environments.
- 5. Learning Effectiveness:** Comparing the learning outcomes and academic performance of MBA students in online and traditional settings offers a deeper understanding of the effectiveness of online education and its potential to match or surpass traditional methods.
- 6. Technological Integration:** The pandemic accelerated the integration of technology in education. Exploring how MBA students adapted to new digital tools and platforms

contributes to a broader understanding of technology's role in enhancing the learning experience.

7. **Mental Health and Well-being:** The pandemic's impact on mental health and well-being is a critical concern. Examining how MBA students coped with stress and isolation during virtual learning can guide the development of support mechanisms for students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE IMPACT ONLINE EDUCATION AMONG MBA STUDENTS DURING COVID-19:

1. Evaluate learning effectiveness and academic performance in online MBA programs.
2. Examine student engagement, resilience, and mental health during virtual learning.
3. Assess the integration of technology and pedagogical innovations.
4. Investigate networking and career opportunities in the virtual landscape.
5. Identify disparities in equity, access, and preparedness for future challenges.
6. Inform policy decisions and future education models for MBA programs.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN COVID-19 AND ONLINE EDUCATION ON MBA STUDENTS:

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on MBA students, prompting a swift transition to online learning as a reaction to the enormous obstacles given by the worldwide health catastrophe. MBA programmes were forced to embrace virtual learning environments very immediately as educational institutions were forced to close their physical campuses to comply with public health regulations. This abrupt change upended the status quo of higher education and offered new chances and challenges to MBA students. The learning process itself was one of the main factors impacted. MBA students have to get used to asynchronous learning, video conferencing, and virtual classrooms as a result of the change to online education.

This modification changed the way that students and instructors interacted, perhaps affecting the calibre of group discussions and collaborative learning. The digital gap has also become a major issue, with some students finding it difficult to participate completely in the online learning process due to differences in access to technology and dependable internet

connections. MBA students also have the option of adjusting their study times and places thanks to the increased flexibility of online learning. However, as students juggled family obligations and academic demands, this flexibility also required improved time management skills. With fewer face-to-face interactions, the change to online learning had repercussions for social interaction and networking, potentially limiting students' possibilities to develop close relationships with their peers and widen their professional networks. The pandemic's effects on some MBA students' mental health and wellbeing further complicated their online learning experience, which might have an effect on their engagement and performance in class.

Despite the difficulties, the transition to online learning caused by the pandemic has brought attention to the value of technology adoption and digital literacy in contemporary education. Developing their digital skills for efficient online learning, MBA students had to swiftly adjust to new virtual tools and platforms. Although the unexpected change initially caused challenges, it also provided opportunities for the adoption of cutting-edge teaching strategies and digital tools that may improve the quality of the educational process as a whole. Another important element was how the epidemic affected assessment and evaluation procedures. Questions concerning the fairness and openness of grading have arisen as a result of the need for faculty to adapt evaluation methods for online contexts. In order to combine flexibility and the advantages of face-to-face interactions, MBA programmes and institutions started investigating hybrid learning approaches as the epidemic spread. These modifications and advancements imply that COVID-19 and online learning have an impact on MBA students that goes beyond the present obstacles and interruptions. How MBA programmes are created, delivered, and technologically integrated in the post-pandemic environment may be affected by the experiences and lessons learnt during this time, which might have long-term effects on higher education. Continue researching this connection, establishing best practises, and utilising technology to improve the educational experience for MBA students as the globe navigates through the pandemic's uncertainty.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Saurabh Phanse ., (2021) This paper shows how online learning affects pupils. The majority of respondents favoured conventional classroom instruction; students could communicate with teachers online; and traditional classroom settings improved students' comprehension of all topics. Exams and courses offered online have the potential to replace those offered offline. Students prefer taking tests online to taking exams on paper, and they also prefer multiple-choice questions over descriptive questions. Even if they don't experience stress when taking online classes, the majority of students continue to believe that traditional classroom training is superior to it. Compared to traditional education, online education is more cost and time effective.

Mohammad Alawamleh, Lana Mohannad Al-Twait and Gharam Raafat Al-Saht ., (2020) “The effect of online learning on communication between instructors and students during Covid-19 pandemic” .This study sought to determine whether online learning negatively impacts student productivity levels and communication between instructors and students. Additionally, to assess and make recommendations for methods to enhance successful communication between professors and students in online courses. Due to the numerous issues students encounter when taking online classes, including their lack of motivation and lack of comprehension of the material, the decline in communication between the students and their instructors, and their increased sense of isolation brought on by taking online classes, the majority still prefer classroom instruction over that offered online. This study demonstrated that communication and its efficacy between instructors and students are certainly negatively impacted by online learning.

Muddassar Sarfraz, Kausar Fiaz Khawaha, Larisa Ivascu., (2022) “The International Journal of Management Education Volume 20, Issue 2, 100630”.This study is concerned with Recent technical developments made e-learning possible during the COVID-19 epidemic, allowing academic tasks to go through more quickly. When creating new technical instruments to meet the demands of students' learning, the BL system offered various benefits to schools. In order to ease learning activities, new online technologies are being adopted quickly by educational institutions all over the world thanks to blended learning methodologies (also known as e-learning).

Ritika Mahajan , Weng Marc Lim, Satish Kumar, Monica Sareen (2023) “COVID-19 and management education: From pandemic to endemic, The International Journal of Management Education”. This research paper has demonstrated that COVID-19's impact on management education has been unprecedented, and that everyone has felt it regardless of their discipline or geographic location (a country, territory, or area). It is remarkable that COVID-19 has had a major practical impact and a correspondingly large scientific interest. In order to protect the future of management education and, by extension, the future of education, it is crucial that future management education research continues to proliferate on a growth and transformative trajectory while remaining mindful of the lessons learned from COVID-19. The research on management education conducted before, during, and after the COVID-19 pandemic and endemic reveals five key themes that, in our opinion, are likely to persist because management education is anticipated to advance rather than regress as a result of the knowledge and understanding gained from the major crisis and mega-disruption caused by COVID-19.

Gurpreet Bagnal, Kaustubh Kanungo.,(2021) “Psychological Impact Of Covid-19 And Online Learning On Higher Education (Mba/Pgdm) Students In India”. According to this study, the respondents predicted a moderate to high degree of stress throughout the study period, which may be related to the existing social and economic conditions governed by Covid-19. Authorities in higher education can offer academic and online counseling to students who are passing through this time when online learning has become the standard. Further research is needed to conduct longitudinal studies on psychiatric disorders like depression and anxiety in order to provide evidence-based mental health interventions during emergencies. Additionally, since this is the first exploratory survey of Indian students, the findings could be utilized as a starting point for research on the causes of stress and anxiety among students in the post-Covid period as well as its effects.

T. Muthuprasad , S. Aiswarya , K.S. Aditya , Girish K. Jha (2021) “Students’ perception and preference for online education in India during COVID -19 pandemic” . The study's conclusions showed that most students in the wake of Corona had a favourable view towards online programmes. Because it gave students flexibility and convenience, online learning was deemed to be beneficial. Students appreciated well-organized information that has published recorded films on university websites. The necessity for interactive sessions with tests and assignments at the conclusion of each lesson was also mentioned as a way to enhance learning. Because of technology limitations, delayed feedback, and the instructor's failure to effectively

manage information and communication technologies, most students also stated that taking lessons online might be more difficult than taking classes in a traditional classroom. Therefore, to make an online course more useful and beneficial for the learner, all these variables should be taken into account while constructing it. After the COVID-19 epidemic subsides, it's possible that educational systems will continue to use online platforms as study aids, but in a hybrid format in addition to conventional classes. As a result, this study will be helpful for revamping higher education to include elements that use the online method.

Hery Winoto Tj. , and Hans Harischandra Tanuraharjo(2020) “The Effect Of Online Learning Service Quality On Student Satisfaction During COVID19 Pandemic” .This study aims to examine and evaluate the impact of online learning's service quality on management students enrolled in the resource management and organisational behaviour course. This study ultimately comes to the conclusion that the quality of the online learning service has a beneficial impact on student happiness once the data have been gathered, analysed, and debated. In order to satisfy the active students who use online learning, the university must prepare and equip (1) the online system with the appealing displays, the precise information, and the sufficient bandwidth, (2) the lecturers as an instructor and a material provider with training, and (3) the administrators with the readiness to help the students.

Pitambar Paudel (2021) “Online Education: Benefits, Challenges and Strategies During and After COVID-19 in Higher Education”. This study looked into the advantages, difficulties, and coping mechanisms of online learning from the viewpoints of instructors and students in Nepal's higher education during and after the COVID-19 epidemic. Even though it was their first time taking purely online courses, the study's findings showed that the participants viewed online education to be advantageous. They discovered that online education is extremely advantageous for boosting online research, tying practitioners to the worldwide community, obtaining vast and authentic information resources needed for professional and academic endeavours, and helping practitioners develop self-discipline.

Latifa Alzahrani , Kavita Panwar Seth.,(2021) “Factors influencing students' satisfaction with continuous use of learning management systems during the COVID-19 pandemic: An empirical study”. During the COVID-19 epidemic, this study analysed and looked at the key elements influencing students' continued usage of LMSs in higher education. An online poll was used to validate a structural research model that was put out. According to the findings, information quality and self-efficacy both had a significant impact on students' happiness

throughout the pandemic, however service quality had little bearing. The results also showed that neither self-efficacy nor satisfaction affected personal outcome expectations, but that prior experience and social influence did, indicating that the COVID-19 epidemic significantly influenced UK students in this dimension. The results have important practical ramifications for education developers, policymakers, and practitioners looking to create effective plans for and enhance the usage of LMSs during COVID-19.

Steve Brammer and Timothy Clark (2020) “COVID-19 and Management Education : Reflections on Challenges, Opportunities, and Potential Futures – British Journal Management”. The type and balance of work in BSs have been significantly impacted by COVID-19. Staff have seen a considerable change in the ratio of research to teaching in their responsibilities, in addition to work intensity and the necessity for quick adaptability and learning. During the current crisis, COVID-19 has placed a greater priority on learning and teaching while lessening its reliance on research. It is crucial that both the professional effects of crisis and concern for how our robust research cultures may be preserved through this and future crises are taken into account.

Zakaryia Almahasees and Khaled Mohsen (2021) “ Faculty’s and Students’ Perceptions of Online Learning During COVID-19”. The study scrutinized the perception of the faculty and students on online learning. The study showed that online education is less effective than online classes. The students of online learning face several challenges due to the struggle to complete adaptation to online courses and the lack of interaction between students and their tutors. E-learning platforms motivate student-centered learning, and they are easily adjustable during abrupt crises, such as COVID-19. The universities in Jordan should take part in training students on how to protect their data. Moreover, the government should advise telecommunication companies to improve the students’ services at an affordable price. It is worth mentioning that students with special needs should have synchronous classes, where the special needs specialists should have a role to facilitate such students’ process.

Ambika Selvaraj and Radhin Vishnu (2021) “ Effect of pandemic based online education on teaching and learning system”. Although the COVID 19 pandemic hit everyone hard, teachers and students quickly resumed their journey by setting up emergency remote learning platforms with various online collaborative tools in hand, even without a pre-planned course structure or proper training for teachers or students to adapt to the change. Regular lessons were

preferred by both the learners' and teachers' groups. Most students said regular sessions were better in terms of efficiency, engagement, and overall comprehension. Although there is some comfort in learning/teaching from home, various technological challenges and the extra work required make the process stressful for students and teachers.

CONCLUSION:

During the COVID-19 epidemic, the influence of online education on MBA students was varied. While it increased flexibility and adaptation to technology, it also introduced new issues in terms of engagement, interaction, and mental health. The long-term ramifications of this transformation are yet unknown, but it likely hastened the incorporation of technology in education and better prepared MBA students for future distant work settings. As the epidemic progresses and education improves, a more thorough knowledge of the effects of online education on MBA students is expected to emerge.

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